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Board of Summary of activities - an innovative approach to streamline timeliness of supervisory activities at Medical Officer of Health offices in Colombo Regional Directorate of Health Services, Sri Lanka

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Background: Timeliness of data reporting is crucial for decision making at all levels. There is no common platform to monitor the timeliness of activities carried out by medical officer of health (MOH) Offices, under maternal and child; disease control and environment and occupational health domains.

Description of the intervention/ initiative: A list of all records and activities with stipulated deadlines was compiled with inputs from all district and MOH-level supervisory officers. A checklist table; 'summary of activities' spanning 52 weeks for 2025 was designed and produced as a board for display at MOH Offices. It displayed each supervisory officer by name, short signature and their assigned return/activity. Supervisory officers were instructed to fill each box with their short signatures and date after completion of relevant tasks. MOHs were instructed to send a photograph of the updated checklist weekly to RDHS Office via email/ WhatsApp for monitoring purposes.

Methods used for the evaluation: The completeness and timeliness in submission of each record/activity according to the stipulated deadlines were assessed.

Results: The 'summary of activities' board was displayed at all MOH offices. There was appreciable compliance with the monitoring mechanism. Rate of timely reporting for 2025 in all categories of returns remain at 90-100% and is a significant improvement in comparison to 2024. Timeliness of immunization clinic returns and school clinic returns which were observed to be low, improved from 64.6% to 100% and 39.1% to 100% respectively.

Lessons learnt: A checklist visualised at a glance could serve as an effective reminder for supervisory officers in the recognition of urgent tasks and timely implementation.

Keywords: Timeliness; Checklist, Summary of activities board

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